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Screening of Metal Complexes for Biological Activity. Part II : Structural and Biological Studies on Iron(II) Oxalate Complexes with Various Nitrogen Donors

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THE study of various transition metal complexes as models for understanding the many biochemical processes requiring metal atoms is very much interesting^{1,2}. The importance and need for the study of transition metal complexes for their biological significance have been stressed in earlier publications^{3,4}. In continuation of the previous work the synthesis of some iron(II) oxalate complexes with ammonia (amm), ethylenediamine (en), aniline (an), *m*-toluidine (*m*-tol), *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-phdi), 1, 10 - phenanthroline (-phen), *N*-methylpiperazine (*N*-mepz), *N*-phenyl piperazine (*N*-phpz), and some of their structural and pharmacological aspects are described in the present communication.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by adding excess of amine to a weighed quantity of iron(II) oxalate suspended in ethanol and shaking the reaction mixture for 5-6 hours. The contents were allowed to stand for another six hours and then filtered, washed with dry ether and finally dried in vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂. However, ammonia complex could be recovered by addition of acetone using differential solubility method.

Iron was determined gravimetrically as Fe₂O₃. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically. Conductance was measured in formamide at 10⁻³M concentration. IR and diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 621 and Cary 14 spectrophotometers respectively using nujol discs.

CNS effects and acute toxicity :

Albinomice of either sex (18-22 g) were used to observe the gross effects and effects on central nervous system (CNS)⁵. For LD₅₀ (the dose level which kills almost 50% of the experimental population) which is customary yard stick of acute toxicity, the test compounds were given intraperitoneally (ip) to the groups of 5 albinomice. They were kept at room temperature of 24 ± 2° and observed continuously for 2 hours and then at two hourly intervals for the next 6 hours. Mortality of the mice during the next 24 hours was recorded and approximate LD₅₀ was estimated.

Anti-inflammatory activity (AIA) :

This test was done on mice at the oral dose of 1/5LD₅₀ according to the technique of Dhawan and Srimal⁶.

Diuretic activity (DA) :

Diuretic effects of the compounds were studied in male albino rats weighing between 200-250g at 1/4 LD₅₀ dose⁷. Chlorothiazide (100 mg/kg. ip) served as the standard for comparison.

Cardiovascular effects (CVS) :

Adult cats (25-40 kg) of either sex, anaesthetized with pentobarbitone sodium (35 mg/kg iv) were employed. The trachea was cannulated and connected to Marey's tambour. One of the common carotid arteries was also cannulated and connected to a mercury manometer. Records were made on a slow moving Kymograph. The drug was administered through a cannulated femoral vein and the effect on blood pressure was studied on the normal blood pressure level and also on pressure response to adrenaline (0.5-1 µg/kg) and depressor responses to acetylcholin and histamine (both 0.25-0.5 µg/kg).

Analgesic activity (AA) :

The analgesic activity was tested by Haffner's Tail Clip method⁸. In this method the mechanical pain was induced by pressing the tail of male rats (90-110g).

Results and Discussion

Analytical, magnetic and spectral data are listed in Table 1 and the results of biological screening are shown in Table 2.

The complexes have been formulated as [FeC₂O₄(L)₂] where L = amm, en, an, tol, phdi, phen, mepz and phpz. Low conductance values (0.25 - 0.40 mhos) show the non ionic nature of the complexes. Lowering of νNH and positive shifting in mixed C=C, C=N and ring vibrations in the IR spectra of all the complexes clearly indicate the coordination of ligand (L) through nitrogen. The coordination of oxalate through oxygen atoms has been confirmed on the basis of considerable negative shift in C-O and positive shift in C=O bands (Table 1)⁹. Fe-N and Fe-O bands have also been observed in lower region of IR spectra of all the complexes which further substantiate the conclusion drawn earlier.

The effective magnetic moments of compound No. 1, 3, 4, 7 and 8 of Table 1 suggested tetrahedral structure, but a band around 6.8 kK in diffuse reflectance spectra suggested C_{2v} symmetry for these complexes¹⁰. On the other hand the compound No. 2, 5, 6 of Table 1 exhibited a broad band centred

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Analysis (%)				Molar conductance (mhos)	IR Spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Diffuse reflectance band nm. (kK)	D _g (cm ⁻¹)	
	Fe	C	H	N		NH	O=C-O	Fe-O	Fe-N				
1. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (amm) ₂]	31.25 (31.40)	13.50 (13.50)	3.35 (3.37)	15.64 (15.75)	0.30	3245 vs 3180 s	1675 vs	1490s	350m	245m	5.27	260 (38.46) 400 (25.00) 1255 (7.97) 1420 (7.04)	750.5
2. [FeC ₂ O ₄ ⁻ (en) ₂]	21.30 (21.16)	27.18 (27.30)	6.10 (6.06)	21.00 (21.22)	0.35	3262 s 3180 s 3160 s	1695 s	1375s	383m	233m	5.60	240 (41.67) 280 (35.72) 365 (27.39) 494 (20.24) 537 (18.62) 600 (16.66) 950 (10.53)	950.0
3. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (an) ₂]	17.00 (16.92)	50.86 (50.95)	3.98 (4.25)	8.50 (8.49)	0.25	3320 s 3200 s	1675 s	1405m	350ms	242m	5.12	1180 (8.47) 248 (40.32) 375 (26.67) 1450 (6.90) 1660 (6.02)	646.0
4. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>m</i> -tol) ₂]	15.50 (15.60)	54.00 (53.67)	5.00 (5.03)	7.68 (7.82)	0.25	3349 vs 3280 vs	1690 s	1358s	358m	267m	5.08	220 (45.45) 260 (38.46) 302 (33.11) 1475 (6.78) 1687 (5.93)	635.5
5. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>o</i> -phdi) ₂]	15.35 (15.52)	47.00 (46.71)	4.28 (4.44)	15.38 (15.55)	0.30	3240 s 3160 m	1700 s	1390m	350m	229m	5.53	239 (41.84) 283 (35.34) 367 (27.25) 442 (22.62) 502 (19.92) 967 (10.34)	958.5
6. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (phen) ₂]	11.00 (11.08)	61.82 (61.94)	3.00 (3.17)	10.98 (11.11)	0.40	*1610 1510 m	1710 vs	1380m	340m	230ms	5.42	250 (40.00) 295 (33.90) 370 (27.03) 495 (20.20) 555 (18.02) 960 (10.42) 1240 (8.07)	924.5
7. [FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>N</i> -mepz) ₂]	16.02 (16.24)	41.76 (41.89)	7.00 (6.98)	16.30 (16.28)	0.35	3250 s 3120 m	1695 s	1390m	358m	298m	5.07	252 (39.68) 340 (29.41) 490 (20.41) 1280 (7.81) 1450 (6.90)	735.5
8. [FeC ₂ O ₄ ⁻ (<i>N</i> -phpz) ₂]	11.80 (11.93)	56.0 (56.45)	5.88 (5.98)	11.84 (11.96)	0.26	3250 s	1708 s	1392s	367s	287m	5.11	248 (40.32) 280 (35.72) 300 (33.34) 1250 (8.00) 1460 (6.85)	742.5

FeC₂O₄ : c-o (sym) at 1338 cm⁻¹, c=o (asym) at 1640 cm⁻¹

* mixed C=C, C=N and ring stretching vibrations of [FeC₂O₄(phen)₂]

around 10.5 kK with a shoulder around 8.00 kK and are believed to belong to O_h symmetry with slight distortion¹¹. A very strong and broad band at 20 kK has been assigned to be a charge transfer band arising from metal to ligand (t_{2g} → π*) charge transfer. The values of μ_{eff} are in consonance with octahedral geometry assigned to these complexes.

All the complexes under investigation stimulated central nervous system. The increased spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivity were due to direct action of the given compound on the effector cells whereas the increased rate of respiration was a result of dilation of bronchioles and direct stimulation of respiratory centre. Tremor, gasping, piloerection and

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TABLE 2—RESULTS OF BIOLOGICAL SCREENING

Compound	Approximate LD ₅₀ mg/kg ip)	CNS activity at 1/5 LD ₅₀	Effects on CVS (Cat) at 2.5 mg/kg i. v.	A. I. A. % inhibition	D. A. at 1/4 LD ₅₀ (%)	A. A. at 1/5 LD ₅₀
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (amm) ₂]	300	Nil	Nil	Nil	40	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (en) ₂]	800	Increased SMA reactivity and resp.	Hypotension 36 mm Hg for 15 mts.	Nil	46	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (an) ₂]	300	Increased SMA reactivity and resp, ataxia, tremor and gasping	Hypotension 20 mm Hg for 10 mts.	26	30	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>m</i> -tol) ₂]	> 1000	Increased SMA reactivity	Hypotension 40 mm Hg for 30 mts	24	32	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>o</i> -phdi) ₂]	200	Increased SMA reactivity and resp., dragging, tremor	Hypotension 15 mm Hg to 15 mts	18	20	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (phen) ₂]	300	Increased SMA, reactivity and resp.	Hypotension 32 mm Hg for 20 mts.	6	Nil	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>N</i> -mepz) ₂]	300	-do-	Hypotension 20 mm Hg for 15 mts.	38	Nil	Nil
[FeC ₂ O ₄ (<i>N</i> -phpz) ₂]	300	Increased SMA, reactivity and tremor, piloerection and straubtail	Hypotension 40 mm Hg for 10 mts	Nil	Nil	Present

Resp.—Respiration, mts=minutes, i. v.=intravenously, i. p.=intraperitoneally, SMA-spontaneous motoractivity.

straub-tail etc. produced in some cases were probably due to pronounced toxicity of test compounds. However, the ammonia complex showed no effect on CNS.

Many complexes of this series exhibited weak anti-inflammatory and diuretic activity except ammonia and ethylenediamine complexes which showed considerable diuretic activity. None of the complexes except [FeC₂O₄(*N*-phpz)₂] possessed analgesic property. However, all the complexes except [FeC₂O₄(amm)₂] produced hypotension ranging from 15-40 mm of mercury for a short duration.

No definite structure-activity relationship could be established because of irregular trend of pharmacological properties of the complexes. However, toxicity of FeC₂O₄·2H₂O (LD₅₀=150mg/kg i. p.) has been found to be reduced considerably on coordination and as a matter of fact the [FeC₂O₄(en)₂] is not toxic at all. [FeC₂O₄(*N*-phpz)₂] and [FeC₂O₄(amm)₂] have been reported to possess pronounced antipassive cutaneous anaphylactic activity in mice⁴.

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